

Societal-Binary, Hyperopia-Myopia or for the first time: Attempting Global Emmetropia

*Hyperopia | far-sightedness *Myopia | near-sightedness *Emmetropia | normalsight

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Introduction| Obligation Of Self-Sustainment

Moral obligation, in short, is when one sees a child that plays with a lighter near a drought experiencing forest, one simply don't lets it play with the lighter there, one takes the lighter away because one, as a grown up, knows the dangers of a bushfire and how easily it spreads, how far it can expand, how difficult it would be to extinguish. One doesn't just feels the need to do something, but that one must act, act out of obligation. The obligation arises due to the child's inability to yet see all the far reaching consequences.

It clearly can see the cause, but not reflect over the full effect, nor can the grown up fully foresee it fully either, but the grown up has reference events, memories of events that were devastating in magnitude, to nature, wild-life, humans, properties and aggregated resources needed for the extinguishing and evacuation. Obligation of self-sustainment is not moral, but regardless what moral one might have it is a question of do we want to keep on or not. It is impossible that 8.3 billion people across 195 countries have the same values and believe in different moral obligations. This is not a moral obligation, but an obligation for self-preservation (sustaining ourselves). This is where the difference lies between moral obligation and existential obligation.

Main Part | Why It Is Us All, Not Any Single One

Now with adults that analogy falls partly away because, who is there to have a moral obligation over adults other than law, the state, again being adults?

As adults we have the right over ourselves, by law there is no one else other than the executive and the legislative that has a moral obligation over us adults. As far as we obey to the country respective law, we are free to do whatever does not violate that law. Even though it would do harm to us, our surroundings, nature and many other examples.

There is a lack thereof. A lack of someone having a moral obligation over all adults, not to talk about an existential one. We end up with some adults being able to create a binary either or:

1. A self-sustaining society
2. A self-terminating society

for all the other members of the respective society. Also there is the total aggregation of all respective societies into one global society, which we undeniably have since the early ages of globalisation. This again leads to overall binary either or tendencies:

1. A self-sustaining world-population
2. A self-terminating world-population

The world-population can have a global tendency to execute stronger myopic growth and thereby not have as fast growth but to be a sustainable one. And it could have a tendency towards executing hyperopic growth and thereby have an accelerated growth compared to more myopic growth tendencies, but thereby exceeding the equilibrium, and on the long-term ending up in an equilibrium that does not maintain habitable one. It becomes self-terminating for a subgroup of its inhabitants.

The global population, with all its societies provides us adults with tools, tools which one could not create totally alone, tools that only several people together could manage.

That entire set-up, working together with several people, in order to create such a tool falls apart if we just distribute advanced tools freely. Right? If building a rifle would take lets say 200 people and 200 others working with the resources mining metal, refining metal, creating machinery, maintaining machinery, logistics, producing lever, slide, barrels etc., producing explosives for the cartridges, a case, a bullet etc. Then only the most skilled, talented, and ethically reasonable person, out of all the 400 people who made it together, would get to use it. Again this is heavily simplified to trace out, to make a point.

Our smartest, hard working, patient people contributed to the production of such tools, and even they could only do so together, we are centuries in the refinement process and

the production process is heavily automated and everyone, regardless the skill to build such a tool, and regardless of the fact that a person has to have a cohort with the person would hypothetically be working together with, gets now access to a tool without needing the cohort any longer. Without being involved themselves either. Even a lonely person without such a dedicated cohort can have a global society, providing a tool this advanced.

The entire workload, the group-spirit, the goal orientation, the production reason/cause-effect relation gets skewed. The tools abilities far exceed what a single being could do to its environment and its society. And thereby, could amplify whatever is being done with the tool, again being binary: entailing both good (collective-sustaining) and bad (collective-terminating) actions.

The acquisition of a firearm or a rifle is strongly restricted for the private person in the EU while alcohol is more easy to access. But there are other countries, such as the USA, with different legislation and regulations (the 2nd amendment to the constitution). Thereby make it possible to acquire such tools by reaching adulthood, 18 years, three years before the legal acquisition of alcoholic beverages at age 21. Which in the most parts of the EU would be legal to acquire by age 16-18, except for scandinavia, where for a prolonged time both acquiring weapons and acquiring alcoholic beverages were more restricted.

There is simply no right and wrong, no good or bad answer for setting a legal age for something, other than a biological transition into adulthood, which most countries in the world independently agree upon. But even here the biological knowledge, and when it increases, should be the ground for a new moral obligation, one for the legislation to take into account. If there is surmounting evidence that we have been reducing the risks as much as possible it creates a moral obligation to do so. So if a lot of 16 year old car drivers end up having the highest accident rate on highways it could lead to adjusting the minimal age for acquiring a drivers license. If now biologists would find out that the adolescent brain is not advanced enough to drive a car until the age of 21, we should adjust to that. But once more there are countries with much denser populations and much less dense populations and broader highways, where it would be no problem to have not fully matured abilities if the adolescent abilities are enough for the less dense population and the broader highways. Whereas it would be recommendable to adjust that somewhere with a much denser population and smaller highways. But also if the adolescent would not be matured enough at 16, but a lot of nursing jobs for old people would benefit from having adolescents drive around to work for the elderly, then the benefit outweighs the risks. But this is up to anyone state, independently.

There is no one fits all answer on that level. But we all together make one outcome only on a global scale, which differs.

We see politics, the legislation and the scientific reasoning behind them are complexly interwoven. It is simply not at all that easy as many would wish it to be.

Also there is the human factor: one of how much satisfaction needs to be obtained for the states self-sustainment from within is maintained, how much dissatisfaction can be handled before the states self-termination from within would be actuated. And also even more difficult, no country, I assume, wants to be outcompeted by someone who is not trying to be sustainable and grow because it is trying to be sustainable and grow. This is only achieved if sustainability is part of a **global agreement** that makes it profitable. Such as not supporting substances that harmed the ozone-layer were profitable.

Looking at tools once more. We have developed medicines with which we could treat ourselves, medicines without which we would die. Split into categories: the ones that go over the counter and are self-administered and the ones that are only given by our most skilled professionals.

Medicines which even the smartest of us can not make solely by themselves, because they lack the equipment, the time to do what hundreds or thousands of people together can do, the purity of the educts which effect the purity of the products aimed for in a standard pharmaceutical company, nor would it be possible to check the polarisation of the substances all alone without other people having planned and build and tested the machines to do so. Nor can a person alone statistically assess how common side-effects are, as well as they would not be able to create new substances by understanding the principles of action. Not without simple, yet potentially fatal, trial and error. No matter how smart a person alone would be, there would be limits to what would be possible, just as with the cartridges and the firearms. The same is true for vaccines, computers, cell phones, chips, vehicles and the like.

Society lives with tools far too advanced for one person. And yet it has to be that way to get all the benefits of them. It is no one single person's fault that we got where we are. But the contributions from all of us. In a back-propagation of choice and action, we do see this is a 'what was first the hen or the egg?'-type of question. We are fairly sure, by the way, it was a proto-hen. Who began looking at an ever greater expansion instead of a maintained sustainability? No one knows, because, as so often, it was not recorded.

We humans and many other animals are tool builders, advancement is our nature. But somewhere along the line we began accumulating knowledge, writing up our knowledge, taught our children centuries of ideas, so that they would be at all capable of extending that legacy.

For the first time in history, in this century 1930-2030 we have to ask ourselves if we have advanced so far that we actually have to look at the binary possibilities of what we can do.

We can **A.** choose not to give everybody access to what they could not achieve to build all alone. And thereby take the risks of what that carries with not having it. Which are many.

Or **B**. Choose to give everybody what they can not achieve to build all alone, and take the risks of what that carries with having it. Which are many as well.

We see choice **A** and **B** have both advantages and disadvantages. So by choosing **B** we managed to make a trade-off between some of the disadvantages of **A** with some of the advantages of **B**, even by accepting the entailed disadvantages.

Choosing **B** I define as **Societal Hyperopia, being a little looser on the disadvantages**. But if we chose **A**, it would be **Societal Myopia, being a little too strict on the advantages**. As we do, for example with vaccines (but we managed that by only making it legal for our most skilled doctors and health system workers to set them).

A good example of Societal Hyperopia and Societal Myopia are Norway and Germany.

Germany (Societal Hyperopia) widely sells homeopathics, not all without prescription either, but still accepting some unknowns for the benefits. But Norway on the other side sells no homeopathics, because of the «føre-var principle» which simply means not accepting any unknown disadvantages for an advantage that includes unknowns. (Societal Myopia).

The problem: Sometimes we have to make decisions, take a risk to see: 'Oh that went wrong' or 'Oh it worked'. Or take no risks and see: 'Oh it was actually good we waited' or 'Oh no it worked, why did we wait?'

There is no in-between sometimes. Sometimes it is not a definite True or False as in Boolean logic, sometimes it is more of an either or until we acquire more knowledge.

We, as a global population, no one single individual, first unknowingly, then knowingly have chosen as overall tendency, the hyperopic, and we now globally try to correct that by applying a global myopic tendency.

We are trying to do, but what has not clearly been formulated:

We try to sight-correct ourselves on a global scale, not one state, all together. We try to keep on, but not so much that we self-terminate. We try to globally obtain emmetropia, while still being compatible, trade profitable. From a pro-emmetropic standpoint we want neither hyperopical approaches nor myopical approaches without growth. We want myopical approaches with growth, to not self-terminate ourselves. And we call it sustainability. But we vastly agree upon it being sustainability with growth, with gain, and without being outcompeted. We thereby aim for the first time in history, to sight-correct ourselves, as a species, in a way nature did before, in a time nature could buffer the effects of our tools and emissions. Binary choices were always buffered, found their new equilibrium. Binary choices are even buffered after self-termination, without us.

Means a new equilibrium that does not favor conditions of human life and many other animalia (animals) and plantae (plants), protista (some algae), fungi life forms and other archaea and other eukarya. But clearly not all living and non-living (such as viruses).

Practically we can not achieve this alone, since not every country has the same socioeconomic abilities nor the same strategy. It's common knowledge that we have to do it all together. And the strategy must be equally profitable and compatible for all.

Some countries give financial help to others to do so. Other countries that have a strong wish to stick with this strategy get financial help and contribute to the strategy both intellectually and by actualizing what must be done for sustainability with growth in their region. And we have countries not having the same strategy, focusing on growth without sustainability, which they make up for by trade of finite resources, before they encounter the same strategy of sustainability with growth. We have countries doing changes for themselves, towards sustainability and growth, without helping others directly, but do so indirectly. And we have countries doing both. We have all kinds of players. And what we as humanity now try is to try to prevent a global self-termination. Which is a difficult task to attempt with 195 countries, without conflict, without disagreements, but we circumvented the ozone layer to be destroyed, we have a real chance to do it again. All together. We have to take actions over words.

Conclusion | Who Takes Action?

The question isn't which child is playing with the lighter or which parent needs to intervene. The deeper truth is: We all contributed to, or are descended from those who contributed to creating a world with an infrastructure sophisticated enough to produce that very lighter. This means the obligation is shared. The responsibility lies with us. This is an existential- instead of a moral obligation. But it is highly important that the challenge is profitable and fair and equal, so it not leaves some in danger by taking part. If all take part there have to be guarantees. We have to make sure that no parent that helps the kid, is in danger by doing so.